

Academic Instructional Practices of Public and Private Elementary Schools: A Framework Model

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 27, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Instructional Practices, Learning Delivery, Learning Assessment, Learning Resources</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6588010</p>	<p><i>In the Philippines, a school's effective instructional practices can be measured by how the school performs in standardized national examination instruments like the National Achievement Test (NAT). With this, the study determined the relationship of schools' academic instructional practices in parallel to the National Achievement Test (NAT) ranking. The study used three variables, learning delivery, learning assessment, and learning resources as predictors of NAT academic success of both public and private schools. Furthermore, this study used a mixed-method specifically the sequential-explanatory method. This method includes the collection and analysis of quantitative data followed by a collection and analysis of qualitative data. The study was conducted in the 20 NAT performing schools in the past five years, S.Y. 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, and 2015-2016, (10) public and (10) private schools of Cebu City division. The result revealed that the variables used in this study, the learning delivery, learning assessment, and learning resources have significantly contributed to the academic success of both public and private schools, therefore, predictors of the result of the National Achievement Test. A model was developed that could assist and uphold both public and private success in instructional academic achievement.</i></p>

Introduction

Henry (2003) believes that the school aims to develop every aspect of a child's life at the heart of education. A school primarily leads in shaping a learning environment that facilitates students learning. Adequate teaching-learning practices are essential to obtain schools' academic success. School success can be determined not only by the outcomes of the students but also by the extent to which they utilize and their human, technical and infrastructural resources that exceed the successful instructional academic teaching-learning process. Academic instructional process advert to those related curricula, provisionally abreast accord so educators in order to improve the academic instructional process for learners.

O' Dwyer et.al (2013) said that effective instructional methods are fundamental to carrying out the objectives of students' results for advancing curriculum. The teaching-learning system refers to the activities teachers carry out in the classroom. Within an educational effectiveness framework, "an effective school is one that has an effect on student achievement". Hence, the way we look at schools nowadays is already a matter of utilizing the school as an imperative input to student and institutional success.

Crow and Crow (2009) that academic achievement is proof of instructional practices in an accustomed field of study. Attainment is emulated by the term to which competence or ability has been transmitted to the students. Lent (2000) stated that schools' success in academic instructional practices in elementary schools has shifted a formula of learners' future in this hugely commutative world. Curriculum success has been one of the primary goals of every school in the instructional proceedings. It is also a supreme goal that every academe is expected to function in all manners. Instructional success is a vital instrument a way in which a teacher and learners are adept at their capability, skills, abilities, and competencies which is an important part of developing career aspirations.

Myson (2000) revealed that students' achievement depends on how effectively the teacher manages the instructional system. As far as instruction is concerned, teachers should try and encourage pupils to discover by themselves. The management of an instructional system is not a task that is done by a single person. It is a conglomeration of efforts and technical skills among the stakeholders including the school and the community-at-large that determine an instructional system that is fit for the community they belong to. This purports the idea that a school operates in a mechanism of ensuring students' achievement while at the same time following a system of procedure that maximizes the potential for development among its main clientele – the students.

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship of schools' academic instructional practices in parallel to the National Achievement Test (NAT) ranking and to develop a model that will assist and uphold both public and private success in their school academic achievement.

Statement of Purpose

This research work aimed to determine the relationship between the academic instructional practices and students' NAT results in public and private elementary schools towards academic success. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What was the trend of the top 10 public and private elementary schools' performance in the National Achievement Test in the past 5 years (2011 to 2016) in terms of English, Science, Math, Filipino, Filipino, and AralingPanlipunan (Social Studies)?
2. What was the level of utilizing instructional practices of public and private elementary schools in terms of learning delivery, learning assessment, and learning resources?
3. What are the predictors of the NAT results based on the domains of instructional practices, namely learning delivery, learning assessment, and learning resources?
4. What were the schools' best instructional practices?
5. What model can be generated based on the findings of the study?

Review of Related Literature

This study focuses on the instructional practices of teaching: the teaching strategy, assessment of learning, and instructional materials, which lead to developing a model that will assist and uphold both public and private elementary schools' academic success.

Learning Delivery. According to Abbey (2003), Pedagogy is the art or science of teaching. Efficient teachers use an assorted of academic instructions because there is no lone, comprehensive accession that meets all settings. Academic instructions, consolidating a character of teaching practices that foothold mental commitment, accordance to the broad world, complementary classroom setting, and acceptance of variation, should be carried out beyond all primary attainments, and subject fields. Academic instructional practices build up the welfare of learners, teachers, and the school community - it improves teaching and learning instruction morale and accord to their function and purpose in school; it shapes society's assurance in the endowment of academic instruction in the school.

Bartley (2007) reinforced that pedagogy is both the vehicle to build up learners' wisdom and the origin of teachers' expert identity. As experts, educators utilize sound judgment to distinguish and relieve the predicament in the instructional process, the teacher makeup every day in the classroom. At their finest, educators are also adept to emulate and assess their system, and generating judiciously and equitably tenable judgments with above conformity, practical restraints, or rational options.

Learning Assessment. The second surrogate measurement in the study is an assessment of learning. Steinberg (2004) said that expert educators make use of a wide range of formal and informal evaluations to monitor the instructional process, diagnose learning issues, and determine what they need to do next to further learning. During the regular classroom activity, they collect information about how learners' success, what they seem to know and be able to perform, and what interests them. In this way, they know what is working and what is not, and are able to make an informed teaching-learning process. Earl (2003) believes that assessment for learning can go a long way in successful student learning. Good assessment entrusts learners to ask reflective questions and consider a variety of instructional practices for learning and ad interim.

Learning Resources. Instructional Materials are used as checks on the teachers' knowledge and means of transmission. They give teachers the air of guidance, coordination, supervision, and more time for a correction in the class lesson (Usman and Adewunmi, 2006). Amadi (2002) has asserted that instructional materials play the role of a stimulant in the teaching and learning process. They introduce a learner to firsthand materials and convey a precious quality of intimacy. Materials help the mind of the learner on what is taught apart from being aids to memory. Furthermore, they make learning and teaching more understandable and real.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed-method design specifically the sequential-explanatory method. This method will have included the collection and analysis of quantitative data followed by a collection and analysis of qualitative data. The survey method was used to identify the teachers' and the students' academic instructional practices in teaching and learning, the evaluation for learning delivery, learning assessment, and the learning resources employed by the teachers. A statistical correlational technique was used to establish the associations between the utilization of instructional practices and the performance of the schools in the National Achievement Test. In the second part of the study, the descriptive technique was used to analyze the verbatim accounts of the respondents gathered through interviews. Class observations along with focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted to determine the teachers' accounts of their classroom practices and the post method parameters employed in their instructions.

Research Environment and Respondents

The study was conducted in the 20 NAT performing schools in the past five years, S.Y. 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, and 2015-2016, (10) public and (10) private schools of Cebu City division. The research generally comprises of two categories of respondents namely the teachers and students of the NAT Top Performing Elementary schools in Cebu City. In this quantitative part, both teachers and students took the survey questionnaire. They were randomly chosen, all of which represented the five subject areas of NAT - English, Math, Filipino, Science, and AralingPanlipunan. In this level, random stratified sampling was utilized to identify the teacher respondents and to validly represent the subject areas aforementioned. The student respondents were chosen through simple random sampling or the fishbowl method. In the qualitative aspect of the study, 10 teacher respondents for every school were identified through purposive criterion sampling. The criteria to identify the teacher respondents will include the following: (1) the teacher must have taught in that elementary school for more than 3 years; (2) the teacher must have taught the following subject areas for grade VI: English, Science, English, AralingPanlipunan and Filipino. On the part of the student respondents, 10 Grade VI students for every school will be identified through convenience sampling to get rid of biases.

Research Instrument and Data Gathering Procedure

A validated survey questionnaire (on the four-point Likert scale: A= always, F= Frequently, O=Occasionally, N= Never) was used in this study covering the pedagogic parameters, learning delivery, learning assessment, and instructional materials in teaching English, Mathematics, Science, Filipino, and Social Studies that reflects the teachers' academic instructional practices that characterized effective teaching and learning. The second instrument used in the study is the interview guide for teachers and students, which consists of open-ended questions regarding personal classroom involvement related to the subject areas.

Permission from the Cebu City public and private schools' division superintendent of the Department of Education Region was sought to conduct the study of the top 10 NAT performing schools. The letter contains the reason why the study was conducted including the data gathering procedure. The school principals were informed and furnished with a letter signed by the Schools Division Superintendent. The selection of respondents was then identified by each school head or principal. The researcher personally explained to the Grade 6 teachers and students chosen as respondents with regards to the rationale of this paper.

Data Analysis

This paper's first set of data that was analyzed in the research were the results of the National Achievement Test. To give meaning to the data, it was analyzed using Trend Analysis. Then, the second and third sets of data dealt with the utilization of the measurement surrogates of the instructional practices. The data will then be analyzed through the weighted mean for each subject area per school. The teachers' academic instructional practices of effective teaching were subjected to statistical analyses that generated descriptive-correlational, a regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between the NAT result and the teachers' academic practices to determine if the practices predicted the performance of the school in the said test.

The qualitative data was accomplished through interviews and naturalistic observation. After properly coding the data, it was triangulated across responses. By triangulating, the data are cross-checked against each other for consistency of responses.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers sought permission from the Ethics Research Board of the university and had the paper reviewed. Once the ERB approved the conduct of the study, permissions were sought from the University President, as well as from the Division Superintendent of Cebu City. Informed consent was asked from the teachers and student respondents. The anonymity of the teachers and students was always observed throughout the investigation of the problem.

Results and Discussion

Trend of top 10 Public Elementary schools in NAT performance for the last 5 years

Fig 1. The National Achievement Test (NAT) Performance of the Top Performing Public Schools from 2012-2016

Legend: Mastered (**M**) 96% - 100%; Closely Approximating Mastery (**CAM**) 86% - 95%; Moving Towards Mastery (**MTM**) 66% - 85%; Average Mastery (**AM**) 36% - 65%; Low Mastery (**LM**) 15% - 35%; Very Low Mastery (**VLM**) 5% - 14%; Absolutely No Mastery (**ANM**) 0% - 4%

The trend as shown in figure 2, public schools revealed that for the past 5 years, Math subject is in the highest rating, ranging from 66% - 85%, Moving Towards Mastery (**MTM**) while the **Science** subject is highlighted as the lowest in rating, ranging from 36% - 65%, Average Mastery (**AM**). This implies that there is a strong reason to believe that in teaching mathematics, teachers' conceptions about the subject and its teaching play an important role in affecting their effectiveness as the primary mediators between the subject and the learners. These conceptions play in the formation of instructional practices or characteristics of the success of their teaching. The above interpretations and implications were supported in the study of Brabeck (2013) as he stated that observations of the curriculum instructional practices are an important factor that would lead to a successful student in Math achievement.

On the other hand, the **Science** subject was highlighted with the lowest rating for the past five years. This means that the teachers lack equal emphasis in all the science curriculum repertoire of competencies reasons for science underachievement. Another reason could be the schools' unstable equipment like the laboratory supplies, books, sufficient learning resources, and the lack of teachers' professional development, all these could affect the results in terms of the learners' achievement in examination and involvement in Science advanced tasks. This implies that the present situation needed to be carried out to possibly rescue science education. This is supported by Senatra (2004) as he pointed out that the teachers need to review instructional benefits and pedagogies in teaching science to merit right in the provisions of the subject competencies' standards and student behavior.

Trend of top 10 Public Elementary schools in NAT performance for the last 5 years

Fig 2. The National Achievement Test (NAT) Performance of the Top Performing Private Schools from 2012-2016

Legend: Mastered (M) 96% - 100%; Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM) 86% - 95%; Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) 66% - 85%; Average Mastery (AM) 36% - 65%; Low Mastery (LM) 15% - 35%; Very Low Mastery (VLM) 5% - 14%; Absolutely No Mastery (ANM) 0% - 4%

The trend as shown in figure 2, private schools disclosed that for the past 5 years the **English** subject has consistently in the highest rating ranging from 66% - 85%, Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) while **HeKasi** subject is **consistently** in the lowest rank for the last 5 years, with the rating ranging from 36% - 65%, Average Mastery (AM). This means that private school teachers are mindful of the relevance of the educators' characteristics in letting the learners achieve more especially in mastering English as a subject. This also means that teachers and students in English subjects have operationalized classroom practices in making learning gains in literacy. This implies evidence that effective English teachers and instructional practices possess a well-developed knowledge base in the subject. This is supported by the study of Chacón (2005) that the pleasure of teaching the English subject and the approaches used in the classroom plus the social prestige of students, to a large extent influence students' comprehension and success in the classroom.

HeKasi's subject is overly critical as it has the lowest rating on the National Achievement Test. The researcher believes that many teachers struggle with finding out **how to motivate students** to learn when teaching **social studies** because so many students find this subject boring. It is also believed that classroom instruction and competencies of the subject have not been mastered by the students and are not given emphasis by the teachers. Another factor that the researcher was taken into consideration based on experience was the use of Filipino or English in the medium of instructions in teaching the subject. This implies that the medium of instruction used in the subject is maybe one of the factors that can promote learning in the subject. This is supported by the study of Gorgonio (2012) students had a low level of instructional academic success in Social studies where the medium of instruction is not Filipino. He then concluded that using Filipino as the medium of instruction of the subject can promote better success in learning.

Table 1. The level of Utilization of the Public and Private School Teachers

Type of School	Subject	Learning Delivery			Learning Assessment			Learning Resources		
		$\bar{x}$	s^2	Description	$\bar{x}$	s^2	Description	$\bar{x}$	s^2	Description
Private	AP	3.61	0.11	Always	3.60	0.10	Always	2.76	0.95	Frequently
	English	3.39	0.13	Always	3.33	0.13	Always	2.75	0.13	Frequently
	Science	3.49	0.22	Always	3.47	0.20	Always	2.81	0.37	Frequently
	Math	3.56	0.07	Always	3.59	0.08	Always	2.44	0.25	Occasionally
	Filipino	3.58	0.11	Always	3.50	0.20	Always	3.06	0.68	Frequently
Public	AP	3.38	0.11	Always	3.20	0.19	Frequently	2.82	0.26	Frequently

English	3.46	0.06	Always	3.48	0.07	Always	2.48	0.14	Occasionall y
Science	3.34	0.16	Always	3.22	0.17	Frequentl y	3.01	0.28	Frequently
Math	3.43	0.09	Always	3.31	0.14	Always	2.29	0.17	Occasionall y
Filipino	3.43	0.13	Always	3.28	0.14	Always	2.52	0.23	Frequently

Legend: A – Always; F – Frequently; O – Occasionally; N – Never; $\bar{x}$ - Mean; s^2 - Variance

The findings in this study, as shown in table 1 have indicated that both public and private school teachers across subject areas have **always** used **learning delivery** to promote learning. At the core of the learning process, learning strategies, or learning delivery is a fundamental recipe to stimulate the desire and energy of students to enhance their learning competencies. To be consistently among the top-performing schools in the National Achievement Test, these schools have successfully implemented effective learning delivery practices that truly made their success in academic achievement. Students play pivotal roles in acquiring learning and these schools have tailored teaching strategies imperative to their academic achievement.

On the experience of students on the level of utilizing instructional practices by both public and private schools, table 2 under **learning delivery** has shown **always** as a result. This means that students have totally acquired learning in the use of teaching strategies. Teaching at any level of education has the sole purpose of ensuring that all learners can acquire information through the strategies used by the teachers and apply those skills. Teaching is a two-way process; therefore, teachers teach, and students learn. Consequently, the researcher also believes that the teachers have carefully employed strategies that best fit the type of learners they have.

Table 2. The level of Utilization of the Public and Private School Students

Type of School	Subject	Learning Delivery			Learning Assessment			Learning Resources		
		$\bar{x}$	s^2	Descripti on	$\bar{x}$	s^2	Descripti on	$\bar{x}$	s^2	Description
Private	AP	3.26	0.10	Always	3.14	0.11	Frequentl y	2.18	0.26	Occasionall y
	English	3.44	0.03	Always	3.42	0.05	Always	2.29	0.22	Occasionall y
	Science	3.30	0.03	Always	3.22	0.07	Frequentl y	2.49	0.10	Occasionall y
	Math	3.47	0.03	Always	3.33	0.02	Always	2.14	0.18	Occasionall y
	Filipino	3.39	0.08	Always	3.33	0.05	Always	2.07	0.31	Occasionall y
Public	AP	3.59	0.06	Always	3.58	0.05	Always	2.78	0.12	Frequently
	English	3.58	0.06	Always	3.58	0.10	Always	2.80	0.06	Frequently
	Science	3.61	0.04	Always	3.61	0.05	Always	2.84	0.12	Frequently
	Math	3.64	0.06	Always	3.58	0.05	Always	2.73	0.06	Frequently
	Filipino	3.55	0.04	Always	3.62	0.06	Always	2.82	0.04	Frequently

Legend: A – Always; F – Frequently; O – Occasionally; N – Never; $\bar{x}$ - Mean; s^2 - Variance

The third surrogate measurement of the study is in the utilization of learning resources. In table 2 the result shows private schools were **occasionally** favored while the public **frequently** favored the use of instructional materials.

On the other hand, **public schools** revealed **frequently** favored the use of learning resources. This means public school teachers provide a variety of instructional materials in the presentation of the lesson content. In addition, it has also been observed that public schools displayed festive learning resources compared to private schools. Facilities are displayed inside the classroom even the comfort room is inside the classroom compared to private schools; this is the reason why public-school students can really feel the presence of learning resources inside the classroom.

Table 3 showed statistically significant results on schools' instructional practices were related to student results on the National Achievement Test for the last 5 years (2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, and 2015-2016). The three instructional practices, Learning Delivery, Learning Assessment, and Learning Resources identified in the data gathering tools on the teacher's and students' questionnaires were statistically significant when examining student achievement. The schools' instructional practices would positively impact students' achievement if they were using sound instructional practices. The results showed the three indicators had a positive impact on student achievement. This result may cause building administrators to more closely supervise teachers to ensure instructional practices do not decrease the effectiveness of the adopted curriculum.

Table 3. The Regression Analysis Results

The regression equation in NAT results = 0.00+0.333LD+0.333LA+0.333LR					
Predictor	Alpha Value	T-Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Constant	0.201	2.0100	0.0091	Reject	Significant
Learning Delivery	0.990	2.6840	0.000	Reject	Significant
Learning Assessment	1.010	2.2553	0.000	Reject	Significant
Learning Resources	0.770	1.4601	0.000	Reject	Significant
S = 0.000		R-Sq = 100%		R-Sq(adj) = 100%	

The first surrogate in the study, learning delivery, has a positive influence on students' successful results in the National Achievement Test. This means that teachers have effectively used and vice-versa effectively influence students' academic success.

This implies that teachers have done their best to provide finery of a teaching strategy that enables students to learn. Therefore, the learning environment along with teachers' skills in the pedagogical use of various learning delivery is important for quality education. All the schools must strive to expose students to the integration of teaching strategies to provide quality learning.

The second indicator of this study is the learning Assessment which also showed a positive influence on student achievement. To improve the quality of classroom instruction, it is necessary to assess the quality of that instruction. Classroom assessment and evaluation are universally used to improve students' knowledge and learning. Assessment and evaluation also give teachers useful information about how to improve their teaching methods.

Lastly, the use of learning resources as it showed positive predictors to National Achievement Test success has also contributed an impact to learning. Therefore, with the use of teaching aids teachers and students would bring concrete experiences which create healthy and happy climates for the teaching and learning to exist.

Cortes' Instructional Model

Thus, this study has captured a model drawn from schools' best practices which believe to be strong evidence of a positive effect on student learning and success in the National Achievement Examination.

Figure 3. Framework Model

Figure 3 Framework model, as shown above, represents the level of instructional practices and a philosophical orientation in application to instructions – the Learning Delivery, Learning Assessment, and Learning Resources plus the two best practices- Lesson Review and Active Learning Practice equals to Academic Success.

Conclusion

Instructional Practices are influenced by one's set of philosophies, beliefs, or systems. Taylor (2005) reiterated that instructional practices that were most successful were those that focused on making meaning out of content. Thus, the instructional practices along with the three variables measured in this study, the Learning Delivery, Learning Assessment, and Learning Resources plus the 2 best practices- Lesson Review and Active Learning Practice equals to Academic Success were playing hardball to effectively meet the academic success of the top 10 public and private schools with their consistent highest rating in the National Achievement Test.

In addition, if given emphasis these two explored mechanisms or best practices- Lesson Review and Active Learning Practice have emerged in making a difference to improve the academic performance of the students. In this view, this mechanism or practice indeed plays a significant contribution on students' desired academic performance.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study, the researcher recommends, first improving the rating of the Hekasi subject, the result creates an impact as to whether the students have captured the concepts of the said subject. If the subject will be delivered properly it would be interesting or inviting, which certainly the students will gain interest to learn the subject and improve their performance.

The second is to empower the use of instructional materials, proper use of available instructional materials supports and advances learning.

Third, the compelling schools' instructional practices along with the commensurable application of learning delivery, learning assessment, and use of learning resources must be carried on advancing NAT performance or school's academic success. Booth (2013) pointed out that when implemented on a regular basis, instructional practices that emphasize sense-making have been found to enhance conceptual understanding and support the attainment of academic success.

Fourth, Adaptation of the two best practices across schools' academic instruction: The Lesson Review and Active Learning Practice.

Finally, the framework model generated from this study “Cortes’ Framework Model” if adopted especially in those schools struggling with their academic performance may guide the public and private schools, curriculum makers, administrators, and teachers to make innovations or review their schema in preparation to the National Achievement Test. If applied, this may further help improve schools’ performance in the National Achievement Test and further contribute to a positive impact on students’ achievement and schools’ prestige.

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